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An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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ASSESSING INFLUENCE OF FLOODING ON SOIL TEXTURE IN AGWAN DODO IN GWAGWALADA AREA COUNCIL, ABUJA

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Abstract: *The study examined the impact of flooding on soil texture in Agwan Dodo in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. The objectives of the study are to: Map and examine the soil texture of flood affected area within Agwan Dodo; investigate the soil composition and particle distribution resulting from flooding in the study area; examine the variation in the soil texture of different locations in the study area; and identify and recommend sustainable soil management practices to mitigate the adverse effects of flooding on soil texture in the study area. Both primary and secondary data were sourced for the study. The soil's textural properties (sand, silt and clay) were analyzed. A total of four (4) samples (arable, upstream, middle and downstream) were used for analysis. The descriptive (mean, standard deviation) and inferential (ANOVA) statistics were used for data analysis. The study revealed that: The soil textural classification at point A1 (43.52%) is sandy clay loam while A2 (39.52%) and A3 (35.52%) are silty loam. The soil textural classification at points B1 (18.8%) and B2 (36.8%) are silty loam while B3 (40.8%) is sandy loam. The soil textural classification at points C1 (42.8%) is sandy loam, C2 (36.8%) is silty clay loam and C3 (30.8%) is silty loam. The soil textural classification at points D1 (12.8%) is silty clay loam while D2 (28.8%) and D3 (41.52%) are silty loam. Across the arable, upstream, middle and downstream, the highest value of sand (43.52%) was recorded on an arable area at A1, and those of silt (62.48%) and clay (40.72%) were recorded at D2 and B1. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicates significant variation in the soil textural classes of arable, upstream, middle and at $p > 0.05$. The study concludes that silt has the highest percentage composition at all the points of arable, upstream, middle and downstream in the study. The study recommended that: The Area Council and FCT governments should develop and implement soil conservation measures such as terracing to mitigate soil erosion caused by flooding; both governments should invest in the development of flood risk mapping and early warning systems to help residents prepare for flooding events; and both governments should support research and development efforts aimed at developing flood-resistant strategies to prevent soil degradation.*

Key words: Flooding, Soil texture, composition and soil management practices

INTRODUCTION

Environmental risks brought on by both climate change and human activity include floods. Flood is perhaps the best example of how humans interact with the environment. They can be found in both developed and developing nations, and

they frequently result in tragic losses of life and property as well as pain, hardship, illness, and starvation. Soil is loosened by catchment floods, and rain and outflow wash it away. A flood happens when a stream runs out of its confines and submerges surrounding areas (Stephen, 2011). Shear tension from overland flow causes soil

particles to split and migrate. When the carrying capacity of the flow is exceeded, detached material settles (Nilsson, 2018). Flooding, most times caused the washing away of topsoil, depleting soil nutrients which resulted in a shortage of crop production. Because flooded soils are anaerobic, microorganisms perish. After a flood, the free oxygen in the soil often decreases in a few days (Liu et al., 2021).

Flooding is a significant environmental phenomenon that profoundly affects the alterations in soil nutrients and texture in the riverbank ecosystem (Neill 1995; Hefting et al. 2004; Yang et al. 2006). According to Banach et al. (2009); Lee et al. (2014); and Lu et al. (2016), floods may encourage the deposition of soil particles on riverbanks and enhance the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil. Nevertheless, additional research revealed that because floods carried away much smaller soil particles, it caused the texture of the soil to deteriorate (Campbell et al. 2002). It was believed that the variations in riverbank elevation and flooding patterns were responsible for the disparate study findings (Saint-Laurent et al. 2014; Ye et al. 2014).

A key indicator of the physical characteristics of soil is its texture, which describes the distribution of various-sized mineral particles in the soil (Neyshabouri et al. 2011; Wang et al. 2014). By cementation and agglomeration with organic matter, these soil particles combine to create soil aggregates. Aggregate formation slows down the pace of the breakdown of organic materials and increases its stability. The amount and size of soil aggregates, as well as how efficiently they integrate with organic matter, are greatly influenced by the size and proportion of soil particles (Ahmadi et al. 2011). According to Crawford et al., (1993) and Zheng et al., (2011), soil organic matter is dependent on soil particle size. Higher proportions of smaller particles (clay

and silt) in the soil lead to slower rates of organic matter decomposition and higher levels of organic matter content (Lin and Li 2001).

Naturally, higher soil concentrations of bigger particles, such as sand, correspond to a lower organic content (Christensen and Straw 1986; Wang et al. 2007). Because soil texture affects soil nutrient concentration and aeration conditions, it is therefore considered a crucial component in assessing soil fertility (Wang et al. 2003; Xu et al. 2013). The stable parent material types of the soil are the main determinants of soil texture. Certain environmental conditions can significantly alter soil texture in addition to these fundamental characteristics (Wang et al. 2003; Wang et al. 2009; Fu et al. 2012).

In Nigeria, there was a significant loss of soil nutrients due to nutrient leaching brought on by floods, as referred to by Okafor and Ibrahim's research (2020). Comprehending the influence of flooding on soil texture is essential for putting into practice suitable soil management tactics, like conservation practices, contour farming, and soil amendment, to lessen the adverse consequences and improve agricultural sustainability in areas susceptible to flooding. This nutrient imbalance can hinder agricultural productivity, necessitating careful management practices to replenish the nutrients and restore soil fertility. It is against this background that this study examines the impact of flooding on soil texture in Agwan Dodo in Gwagwalada Area Council.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study area is a suburb of the FCT, situated about 55km south-west of Abuja City centre, between latitude 8°49' and 9°04' North of Greenwich meridian and longitudes 6°50' and 7°06' East of the meridian (Abuja Guide, 2002). It

is bordered in the South by Kwali Area Council, in the North by Niger State; Kuje Area Council in the South East and Abuja Municipal Area Council in the North East. The study area occupies 1,043 km² (Gwagwalada Master Plan, 1980). The geology of the FCT is the same as that of Gwagwalada (Dikedi, 2012). Groundwater is found mainly in the variable weathered/transition zone and fractures, joints and cracks of the crystalline basement while a sparse

amount of water can be obtained in the freshly unweathered bedrock below the weathered layers (Eduvie et al., 2003). The types of rocks found in Gwagwalada include metamorphic and igneous rocks, generally, the rocks are highly sheared. Also, the types of soil in Gwagwalada are generally shallow and sandy. The high sand content particularly makes the soil to be highly erodible (Haruna, 2005).

Figure 1: Map of Federal Capital Territory showing the Study Area
 Source: ArchMap, 10.1

Table 1: Sample Point Geographical Coordinates

Location	East	North
A1	7.098	8.941
A2	7.097	8.94
A3	7.1	8.938
B1	7.095	8.941
B2	7.095	8.94
B3	7.095	8.939
C1	7.099	8.943
C2	7.1	8.942
C3	7.101	8.941
D1	7.103	8.945
D2	7.104	8.943
D3	7.103	8.942

Figure 2: Mapping of Sampling Area

Figure 1 shows the mapped sampling area selected for the study. The figure shows the four (4) areas of; Arable land (A1, A2 A3), Upstream (B1, B2, B3), Middle stream (C1, C2, C3), and Downstream (D1, D2, D3).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data obtained were duly computed and presented using descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation to summarize the data. The one-way analysis of variance was performed to find out if there is a significant variation between the soil textures of the four soil sample points, for statistically different parameters at probability 5% ($p \leq 0.05$). Also, a soil textural triangle was used to determine the soil types.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

SOIL TEXTURE OF ARABLE LAND IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 2 shows the soil textural properties of the arable land at points A1, A2 and A3 in the study area. The table shows that point A1 has a sand composition of 43.52%, silt composition of 41.76% and clay composition of 14.72%. Point A2 has a sand composition of 39.52%, silt composition of 45.76% and clay composition of 14.72%. Point A3 has a sand composition of 35.52%, silt composition of 43.76% and clay composition of 20.72%. The table revealed that the soil textural classification at point A1 is sandy clay loam while A2 and A3 are silty loam respectively.

Table 2: Soil Texture of Arable Land

Locations	Categories of Soil	Percentage (%)	Soil Textural Classification
A1	Sand	43.52	Sandy clay loam
	Silt	41.76	
	Clay	14.72	
A2	Sand	39.52	Silty loam
	Silt	45.76	
	Clay	14.72	
A3	Sand	35.52	Silty loam
	Silt	43.76	
	Clay	20.72	

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024

SOIL TEXTURE OF UPSTREAM IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 3 shows the soil textural properties of the upstream at points B1, B2 and B3 in the study area. The table shows that point B1 has a sand

composition of 18.8%, silt composition of 40.48% and clay composition of 40.72%. Point B2 has a sand composition of 36.8%, silt composition of 38.48% and clay composition of 24.72%. Point B3 has a sand composition of 40.8%, silt composition of 36.48% and clay composition of 22.72%. The table revealed that the soil textural classification at points B1 and B2 is silty loam while B3 is sandy loam.

Table 3: Soil Texture of Upstream

Locations	Categories of Soil	Percentage (%)	Soil Textural Classification
B1	Sand	18.8	Silty loam
	Silt	40.48	
	Clay	40.72	
B2	Sand	36.80	Silty loam
	Silt	38.48	
	Clay	24.72	
B3	Sand	40.80	Sandy loam
	Silt	36.48	
	Clay	22.72	

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

SOIL TEXTURE OF MIDDLE STREAM IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 4 shows the soil textural properties of the upstream at points C1, C2 and C3 in the study area. The table shows that point C1 has a sand composition of 42.8%, silt composition of 36.8%

and clay composition of 20.72%. Point C2 has a sand composition of 36.8%, silt composition of 38.48% and clay composition of 24.72%. Point C3 has a sand composition of 30.8%, silt composition of 48.48% and clay composition of 20.72%. The table revealed that the soil textural classification at points C1 is sandy loam, C2 is silty clay loam and C3 is silty loam.

Table 4: Soil Texture of Middle Stream

Locations	Categories of Soil	Percentage (%)	Soil Textural Classification
C1	Sand	42.80	Sandy loam
	Silt	36.80	
	Clay	20.72	
C2	Sand	36.80	Silty clay loam
	Silt	38.48	
	Clay	24.72	
C3	Sand	30.80	Silty loam
	Silt	48.48	
	Clay	20.72	

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

SOIL TEXTURE OF DOWNSTREAM IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 5 shows the soil textural properties of the downstream at points D1, D2 and D3 in the study area. The table shows that point D1 has a sand composition of 12.8%, silt composition of 60.48%

and clay composition of 26.72%. Point D2 has a sand composition of 28.8%, silt composition of 62.48% and clay composition of 8.72%. Point D3 has a sand composition of 41.52%, silt composition of 58.48% and clay composition of 8.72%. The table revealed that the soil textural classification at points D1 is silty clay loam while D2 and D3 are silty loam.

Table 5 Soil Texture of Downstream

Locations	Categories of Soil	Percentage (%)	Soil Textural Classification
D1	Sand	12.80	Silty clay loam
	Silt	60.48	
	Clay	26.72	
D2	Sand	28.80	Silty loam
	Silt	62.48	
	Clay	8.72	
D3	Sand	41.52	Silty loam
	Silt	58.48	
	Clay	8.72	

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

VARIATIONS IN SAND SOIL TEXTURAL CLASS IN THE STUDY AREA

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the sand soil textural class of arable, upstream,

middle and downstream in Table 5 indicate that there is significant statistical variation among the various classes of sampled soils at $p > 0.05$. The table revealed that the sand, silt and clay vary significantly $p > 0.05$.

Table 6: Mean Variation of Sand Soil Textural Class

Area/Points	A1	B1	C1	D1	p-value
Arable	0.03	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.10
Upstream	0.01	1.3	2.3	1.1	0.41
Middle	0.02	0.1	0.1	1.1	0.20
Downstream	0.04	1.2	0.4	0.2	0.22
Mean ± SE	1.01	1.30	0.2	1.2	-

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

VARIATIONS IN SILT SOIL TEXTURAL CLASS IN THE STUDY AREA

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the silt soil textural class of arable, upstream,

middle and downstream in Table 6 indicate that there is significant statistical variation among the various classes of sampled soils at $p > 0.05$. The table revealed that the sand, silt and clay vary significantly at $p > 0.05$.

Table 7: Mean Variation of Silt Soil Textural Class

Area/Points	A2	B2	C2	D2	p-value
Arable	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.11
Upstream	0.02	1.1	2.2	1.0	0.31
Middle	0.02	0.3	0.1	1.1	0.21
Downstream	0.03	1.1	0.2	0.1	0.20
Mean ± SE	1.00	1.10	0.2	1.1	-

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

VARIATIONS IN CLAY SOIL TEXTURAL CLASS IN THE STUDY AREA

The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the clay soil textural class of

arable, upstream, middle and downstream in Table 7 indicate that there is significant statistical variation among the various classes of sampled soils at $p > 0.05$. The table revealed that the sand, silt and clay exhibit significant variation at $p > 0.05$.

Table 8: Mean Variation of Clay Soil Textural Class

Area/Points	A3	B3	C3	D3	p-value
Arable	0.01	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.11
Upstream	0.21	1.3	2.1	0.1	0.21
Middle	0.02	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.20
Downstream	0.01	1.2	0.3	0.2	0.10
Mean ± SE	1.11	1.20	0.1	1.0	-

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

Comparison of Soil Textural Classes Across Selected Points in the Study Area

Table 9 Comparison of Soil Textural Classes Across Selected Points

Arable	(%)	Upstream	(%)	Middle	(%)	Downstream	(%)
A1	43.52	B1	18.80	C1	42.80	D1	12.80
	43.52		40.48		36.80		60.48
	*14.72		40.72		*20.72		26.72
A2	39.52	B2	36.80	C2	36.80 38.48	D2	28.80
	45.76		38.48		24.72		62.48
	*14.72		24.72				*8.72
A3	35.52 43.76	B3	40.80	C3	30.80	D3	41.52
	20.72		36.48		48.48		58.48
			22.72		*20.72		*8.72

Source: Field Data Collection, 2024.

Table 9 compares the three (3) soil textural classes (sand, silt, clay) of A1-A3 (Arable), B1-B3 (Upstream), C1-C3 (Middle) and D1-D3 (Downstream). The table shows that in all three (3) locations (A1, A2, A3) for the arable area for soil textural classes (sand, silt, clay), the highest value of sand (43.52%) on arable was recorded at A1 with the lowest (35.52%) at A3. The highest value of silt (45.76%) on arable was recorded at A2 with the lowest (43.52%) at A1. The highest value of clay (14.72%) on arable was recorded at A1 and A2 with the lowest (20.72%) at A3. In all three (3) points (B1, B2, B3) for the upstream area for soil textural classes (sand, silt, clay), the highest value of sand (40.8%) upstream was recorded at B3 with the lowest (18.8%) at B1.

The highest value of silt (40.48%) upstream was recorded at B1 with the lowest (36.48%) at B3. The highest value of clay (40.72%) on silt was

recorded at B1 with the lowest (22.72%) at B3. In all three (3) points (C1, C2, C3) for the middle area for soil textural classes (sand, silt, clay), the highest value of sand (42.8%) in the middle area was recorded at C1 with the lowest (30.8%) at C3. The highest value of silt (48.48%) in the middle area was recorded at C3 with the lowest (36.8%) at C1. The highest value of clay (24.72%) in the middle area was recorded at C2 with the lowest (20.72%) at C1 and C2. In all three (3) points (D1, D2, D3) for the downstream area for soil textural classes (sand, silt, clay), the highest value of sand (41.52%) in the downstream area was recorded at D3 with the lowest (12.8%) at D1. The highest value of silt (62.48%) in the downstream area was recorded at D2 with the lowest (58.48%). The highest value of clay (26.72%) downstream was recorded at D1 with the lowest (8.72%) at D2 and D3. The table revealed that across the arable, upstream, middle and downstream, the highest

value of sand (43.52%) was recorded on the arable area at A1, those of silt (62.48%) and clay (40.72%) were recorded at D2 and B1.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study revealed that at location A1 (43.52%), the soil textural categorization is sandy clay loam; at points A2 (39.52%) and A3 (35.52%), it is silty loam. While B3 (40.8%) has sandy loam, sites B1 (18.8%) and B2 (36.8%) have silty loam soil textural classifications. At positions, C1 (42.8%), C2 (36.8%), and C3 (30.8%), the soil textural categorization is silty clay loam, sandy loam, and silty loam, respectively. While silty loam is the soil textural categorization at sites D2 (28.8%) and D3 (41.52%), silty clay loam is present at D1 (12.8%). The soil texture classes of arable, upstream, medium, and at $p > 0.05$ show considerable variation, according to the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The greatest values of silt (62.48%) and clay (40.72%) were found at D2 and B1, respectively, whereas the highest values of sand (43.52%) were found on the arable land at A1.

These findings are in agreement with the findings of; Dishan et al. (2020) who found out that all physical properties except bulk density were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) between upland and flooded forest soils. Also, Chima (2018) revealed sandy loams which are easily vulnerable to erosion as a result of their properties. The physical properties indicated that the order of susceptibility to erosion was arable land < fallowed floodplain < cultivated floodplain < erosion site. Equally, Njoku and Okoro (2015) also revealed that there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference among the different meadows and control studies. Control recorded the highest bulk density of 1.59gcm⁻³. This observed bulk density in control was

higher than the bulk density in cultivated flood meadow, a year fallowed flood meadow and more than a year fallowed flood meadow by 9, 17 and 22%, respectively. Agwumafa *et al.* (2021) findings also revealed that 20.25%, 51.66% and 28.09% of the entire study area were lowly vulnerable, moderately vulnerable and highly vulnerable to flood. Similarly, 0.3%, 45.7% and 54.8% were lowly exposed, moderately exposed and highly exposed to flood.

However, 14.3%, 28.3% and 57.4% of the study area had low flood risk, moderate flood risk and high flood risk respectively. Ubuoh *et al.* (2016) showed that apart from sand, BD, and gravimetric moisture that was higher in control, silt, clay and porosity recorded the highest mean values than control. Nura and Alison (2022) opined that the northern part of Nigeria is affected more by flooding than the south, so should be prioritized for flood management. Vincent et al (2014) revealed that a significant effect of flooding was observed on soil properties on the flood-affected farmlands when compared to the control farmland, which was statistically justified at a 95% confidence limit ($p \leq 0.05$). The summary of the implications of this current finding is basically on the soil nutrient loss.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that silt has the highest percentage composition at all the points of arable, upstream, middle and downstream in the study, therefore it is recommended that implementation of soil conservation measures such as terracing to mitigate soil erosion caused by flooding, these measures will help maintain soil texture and structure, reducing the adverse effects of flooding on soil quality. Government at all levels should invest in the development of flood risk mapping and early warning systems to help residents prepare for flooding events.

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